

Book Review

Dan Brown, *Origin*, (USA: Doubleday, 2017), Price: Rs. 799.00, Pages: 461.

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“Where do we come from? Where are we going?”.... These are the universal questions that most human beings have been trying to grapple with since centuries. Will we ever get the ‘real’ answer? Have we been successful in looking back thousands of years into history or a thousand years ahead into the future of mankind? No doubt, there have been many curious speculations about both of these pressing questions. But, can a scientist claim with full certainty that it all started with a big bang or can a faithful (or religious cleric) claim with all certainty that it all started with a breath from the God who created Adam and Eve?

In this particular issue, science and religion have always been at loggerheads with each other and this is the central theme of Mr. Dan Brown’s ‘Origin’. Is the Creator God? or is ‘today’ the summation of just a simple scientific evolution? Mr. Brown has tried to explore this heavy topic in his latest fictional work titled ‘Origin’. He is a modern American author famous for his titillating mystery thrillers. His iconic character, Mr. Langdon, a character that he repeats in most of his works, is a professor of Symbology at Harvard University, who always manages to strangely land in the middle of some unimaginable situation, the extrication from which needs an in depth knowledge of religious symbols, arts and mythologies. The respected professor is able to decode and decipher certain ciphers (which keeps the audience enthralled) leading the reader through an adventurous journey to a surprising end. Like always, from “Da Vinci code” to “Angels and Demons”, Brown weaves his narrative very adeptly combining the ancient with the modern. Modern physical spaces and technologies are entwined with ancient, mostly religious symbols and ideas. Thus, he tries to take the reader through the complex world of tradition and individuality.

As in his last book *Inferno*, 'Origin' starts with a prologue. The prologue is always at the heart of his narrative. In this book, Edmond Kirsch, the famous scientist and futurist, has discovered 'scientific' answers to the questions quoted at the beginning of this article. He is supposedly all set for shaking the very roots of all the religions by broadcasting his discovery to the world. However, he is unable to do it. He is killed or rather assassinated before he gets a chance to deliver the answer, dragging the attention of the whole world towards his mysterious discovery. This is where our dear professor Langdon enters the scene. Edmond being his former student, he feels that it is his moral duty to break the suspense and release was all the answers as planned by his friend and student, Kirsch.

Ambra Vidal, the central female character in the book is the future queen of Spain, who also happens to be a curator of Guggenheim Museum, is in-charge of the 'Kirsch's event'. The Guggenheim Museum is actually located in Spain but Dan Brown's description of its architectural wonders makes one to want to really visit it to confirm that it can really be so awe-inspiring. Ambra Vidal and Robert Langdon come together and decide to fulfil Kirsch's wish. Then, enter Winston.... How can we forget Winston? Winston is Kirsch's personal assistant, but, surprisingly, not a human. It is a computer bot or artificial intelligence (AI) created by Edmond Kirsch. It is this unimaginable leap in the field of AI that seems to be the central revolving theme of 'Origin'. Winston, the computer, almost seems human at times. Though purportedly 'programmed' by Edmond, it has such a marvellous programming with life-like abilities and emotions, that sometimes one wonders if Brown has gone a bit too far. The second half of the novel, shows Winston's undeniable presence which could easily be doubted for as that of a 'real' human.

On the other hand, the portrayal of the negative characters like Bishop Valdespino as well as the Jewish and Muslim leaders is somewhat unnatural. One really wonders if any such discovery, which may prove the origin of the universe, as otherwise than what religions believed, can cause any harm to religions or God, for that matter and shake the beliefs of billions of people, so much so that people are murdered over it. The whole idea of shaking of the world religions due to some scientific discovery seems exaggerated and the only weak link in Brown's story. Finally, after deciphering a 47 line poem of William Blake (a typical Brownian thing: ciphers and deciphering), they are able to release the video of Edmond's discovery worldwide.

In the end, the long-awaited climax shatters the really spell binding suspense. Not going into mathematical and technical details, the Edmond's discovery

proves to be a rectified version of the Miller Urey experiment. Seemingly, he has achieved answers to two questions. Where we come from? In simple terms, his answer is we come from a bio-chemical process and not from God. Where are we going? This answer is more terrifying. According to him, another 'species' will take over human beings in next few decades. Technology! Or artificial Intelligence! ... not very different from Winston who was instrumental in the assassination of his creator, Edmond at Edmond's request. Yes, Brown underlines the fact that technology is growing at such a speed, that after a few decades it will be entangled with human life. This book is a significant comment on the growing field of AI and serves more as a cautionary tale.

The book has also tried to explore the possibilities and limits of technological advancement. It reminds us humans, again and again of the moral check that we must all perform in order to preserve what defines us as human beings; our very 'humanness'. It is also a very sharp comment on the field of Artificial Intelligence. Finally, it asks us certain questions. Will the dystopian world of machines without human hands come true? Will the machine start thinking? Should we develop AI without any check? What is a human without faith? It is interesting to note that, in the end, Langdon takes a sigh of relief when he is away from Winston, the AI bot. He feels 'human' again. The last question which the book asks and which gets imprinted on our sub consciousness is, "What if machines stop?"